

Strathmore
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Deliverable

Guidelines for incorporating CEP template-tool updates

Task 5e

31/03/2025

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Module 1: Introduction to Data Lifecycle and Data Quality for Energy Data

Course Overview

This course provides a basic understanding of the data lifecycle and data quality in the context of energy planning in Kenya. Participants will explore legal frameworks, best practices, and practical applications of data management principles to improve energy planning and decision-making.

Intended Learning Outcomes:

By the end of this course, participants will be able to:

- Understand the importance of data lifecycle management and data quality in energy planning.
- Identify the various stages of the data lifecycle within the public sector context.
- Identify key indicators of data quality and their implications for energy planning.

Course Structure

The course consists of three modules, each following a consistent format:

- Introduction: Overview of key themes in the module.
- Course content: In-depth exploration of the topic.
- Exercises: Practical activities for deeper understanding.

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Module 2: Data lifecycle in the public context

Introduction

The data lifecycle represents the structured approach to plan, collect, prepare, analyse, visualize, access, share, use, archive, store and delete data (Abraham et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2021). Various definitions exist, with some including additional steps depending on the industry. However, we believe it is most relevant to focus on the public sector and, therefore, adopt the approach proposed by Shah et al., 2021.

Data lifecycle in the public sector

In the context of energy planning, especially for countries like Kenya, managing large volumes of energy-related data is critical for informed decision-making, transparent governance, and ensuring sustainability. The data lifecycle framework proposed by Shah et al. (2021) offers an effective methodology for managing this data, from collection to protection.

The framework has five critical phases—collection, preparation, analysis, sharing, and use—and five optional ones—planning, visualization, access, archive and end of life—that can be applied directly to energy data in Kenya. The following box presents some details on these stages:

Box 1. Data Lifecycle Framework for data-driven governments (Shah et al., 2021)

- **Planning (optional):** Illustrates activities to be performed in the medium and long terms during the data lifecycle.
- **Collection (mandatory):** Set of activities through which data is gathered from different sources and in different formats.
- **Preparation (mandatory):** Data integration, filtering and enrichment.
- **Analysis (mandatory):** Developing data analysis to extract knowledge and discover new insights
- **Visualization (optional):** Presentation and visualization of the outcomes.
- **Access (optional):** Ways of communication between the data provider and data consumer.
- **Share/Publish (mandatory):** Determine what data can and should be shared and published with appropriate security measures
- **Use, re(use) & feedback (mandatory):** Discovering new and valuable information from datasets and provide feedback.
- **Archive (optional):** Keeping a record for obsolete data
- **End of life (optional):** Duplicated and useless data is removed from the system
- **Storage (performed throughout the lifecycle):** Save data securely

Access to data

In Kenya, the Access to Information Act, 2016 mandates that organizations, both public and private, appoint an Information Access Officer responsible for proactively disclosing

and processing access requests. This regulation directly impacts the data lifecycle, particularly the access phase, by assigning a designated role to handle these requests efficiently. To better understand how data access functions within this framework, we can examine the data acquisition workflow:

- The requester identifies a specific task requiring data.
- The requester accesses a data catalog to review available and relevant data sources.
- Upon identifying the relevant dataset, the requester submits an access request.
- Governance controls ensure the request is forwarded to the appropriate authorizing personnel.
- Once approved, access is granted to the designated data repository.

Reflective exercise

How is data requested in your organization? Define the data acquisition workflow, ensuring you include the role of the Information Access Officer.

Solution

There is no single correct answer—this is just one example of how a data acquisition workflow might be structured. However, best practices suggest having at least two levels of approval to ensure proper governance and security.

Module 2: Data quality

Introduction

Data quality is defined as the ability of data to satisfy its usage requirements across any stage in its life cycle (Abraham et al., 2019; Moses et al., 2022). In the context of energy planning and energy modeling, high-quality data is essential for making accurate forecasts, optimizing resource allocation, and ensuring effective policy decisions. Poor

data quality can lead to flawed energy demand projections, inefficient infrastructure investments, and suboptimal policy outcomes.

Data quality indicators

There are different approaches to data quality, each focusing on ensuring that data is accurate, reliable, and fit for its intended purpose. Some of the most common indicators used to assess data quality include:

Data quality indicators (Informatica, n.d.).

Indicator	Description
Accuracy	Ensures data correctly represents real-world values.
Completeness	Ensures all required data is present without missing values.
Consistency	Ensures uniformity across different datasets and systems.
Timeliness	Ensures data is up to date and available when needed.
Uniqueness	Ensures no duplicate or redundant data entries exist.
Validity	Checks that data conforms to predefined formats and rules.

However, in the context of energy planning, it is important to have data that accurately represents the conditions of the system and can be effectively analyzed for modeling purposes. These specific characteristics help define data quality metrics. Determining which aspects of data quality are most important depends on the intended use of the data, guiding the assessment process. For example:

When creating a plan for electrification geospatial datasets indicating population density, existing grid infrastructure, and energy consumption trends are used. If a dataset contains outdated (timeliness issue) or incomplete (completeness issue) records of electrified villages, it could lead to misallocated resources, such as planning new connections for already electrified areas or failing to prioritize regions that remain off-grid.

Reflective exercise

Think about the data your organization uses for energy planning. Which data quality indicators are most relevant to your work? How would you assess and improve them?